

ON THE STRENGTH OF COMPOSITES WITH HETEROGENEOUS REINFORCEMENT

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ABSTRACT

The present paper describes a semi-analytical multiscale model of the tensile response of unidirectional brittle-matrix composites with heterogeneous reinforcement. At the micro scale, the fiber-matrix interaction in a composite crack bridge is formulated by a shear-lag model with parameters defined as random variables. This randomness results in a non-uniform stress state among individual fibers. A homogenized representation of this heterogeneous reinforcement in the crack bridge is achieved by utilizing probabilistic fiber-bundle models. These representative crack bridges are applied at the macro scale to simulate the strain-hardening response of a multiply cracked composite subjected to tensile loading. The interaction of adjacent crack bridges is reflected by symmetry of their state fields. The model thus provides the whole pseudo stress-strain response including ultimate failure, crack density and crack widths evolution. The modeling framework is validated by comparing its prediction to experiments conducted with textile reinforced concrete.

1. INTRODUCTION

The toughening effect of fibers used as reinforcement in ceramics is well known [1, 2, 3]. Provided that the interface layer allows for debonding and sliding of the fibers along the matrix, the notch sensitivity, thermal shock resistance and fracture toughness of fibrous composites can be significantly increased. If matrices with rather low tensile strength (e.g. cement-based matrices) are reinforced with high-strength ceramic or polymer fibers, the aim is not only to increase the toughness but also to achieve a favorable quasi-ductile tensile behavior and increase the strength [4, 5, 6]. The quasi-ductility is caused by multiple cracking of the matrix and fiber debonding. In general, these composites, which are the focus of the present article, can be called brittle-matrix composites (BMC).

The aim in designing unidirectional BMCs loaded in tension will be that after reaching the saturated state (saturation with matrix cracks) a high bearing capacity is available before the ultimate failure due to localized fiber damage is achieved [2, 7, 8, 9]. The whole process of the composite tensile response is accompanied by considerable stress redistribution both between and within the composite constituents. The qualitative and quantitative characteristics of BMCs strongly depend not only on the material and geometric properties of the constituents and their interface [2, 7] but also on their statistical variability [4].

In order to avoid expensive numerical calculations, which are often highly redundant, many research teams have focused on multiscale models that employ homogenization techniques and scale linking. For the analysis of the microscale mechanics of RVEs (representative volume elements) in fibrous composites, finite element method [10], shear-lag analysis [11], Green's function method [12, 13] or the fiber

bundle model with equal load sharing [14, 15, 16, 17, 18, 19] have been, among others, used in the past. With the RVEs, behavior of larger scaled domains can be extrapolated using appropriate analytical or numerical methods that take into consideration the variability of the RVE properties and the related size-effects.

The major extension of the present model compared to most existing models is the inclusion of randomness in bond properties τ , which introduces heterogeneity into the reinforcement at the microscale. Although the problem of bond heterogeneity has been addressed e.g. in [20, 21], its effect on the tensile response of multiply cracked unidirectional composites has not yet been thoroughly analyzed by efficient probabilistic models. In [4], a probabilistic model was applied for the evaluation of the tensile response of a single composite crack bridged by heterogeneous reinforcement with the assumption of a infinitely stiff matrix. The main conclusion of the paper was that a higher reinforcement heterogeneity reduces the composite strength and increases its toughness, which was also observed experimentally in [20]. In the present article, we extend the model due to [4] by A) The evaluation of the stress state of the matrix and B) The interaction of serially coupled crack bridges.

Given these extensions, a representative crack bridge can be formulated and employed within the multiple cracking model introduced in the present article. According to a review article by Castelier et al. [22], three modeling approaches to the multiple cracking with random matrix strength have been considered so far: random strength approach; random crack approach; continuous approach. All of these models are analytical or semi-analytical and incorporate both matrix and fiber strength randomness. However, a model from this computationally efficient category that involves the micromechanical representation of additional sources of randomness (bond strength, fiber radius, fiber orientation, fiber stiffness etc.) has not been formulated to date.

In the present article, we introduce a generic algorithm for the matrix fragmentation process and its coupling with the a micromechanical crack bridge formulation. In particular, we describe the incorporation of the probabilistic crack bridge model based on the fiber-bundle homogenization. Due to this separation of scales, the tensile response of a composite with arbitrary sources of randomness can be evaluated.

The paper is organized as follows: In Sec. 2, the probabilistic multiscale model and scale linking are described. Sec. 3 presents a calibration and validation of the model against data obtained from tensile tests with textile reinforced concrete. Finally, the model is discussed and conclusions are drawn in Sec. 4.

2. PROBABILISTIC MULTISCALE MODEL

We develop the probabilistic multiscale model in two steps. In the first step, a representative crack bridge is formulated and the probabilistic homogenization of its strain field is introduced. In the second step, we formulate the multiple cracking model which employs a serial coupling of the representative crack bridge units.

2.1 Probabilistic crack bridge model

A single crack bridge in a unidirectional fiber reinforced composite with constant cross-sectional area A_c and a volume fraction V_f of continuous fibers loaded in tension with the far field composite stress σ_c is considered. Both fibers and matrix are linear elastic with moduli of elasticity E_f and E_m , respectively, and fibers fail in a brittle manner upon reaching their breaking strain ξ . This breaking strain refers to the fiber strain at the position of a matrix crack ε_{f0} (see Fig. 1). Fibers are assumed to have circular cross-section with radius r , cross-sectional area A_f and a constant frictional interface stress τ that equals the bond strength so that the bond vs. slip law is assumed ideally plastic with infinite initial stiffness. Justified by the weak bond and high matrix stiffness characteristic for ceramic matrix composites, we consider only the longitudinal deformation of both fibers and matrix and neglect shear deformations [9].

The matrix crack is assumed to be planar and perpendicular to the loading direction. Any residual force transferred by the matrix crack planes is neglected so that the force is transmitted solely by the

Figure 1. (a) Multi-scale modeling approach diagram; (b) diagram depicting the crack bridge response with various control variables.

fibers. Between the crack planes, fibers bear the applied load and then transmit it into the matrix along a debonded length a which depends on the constituent properties and the crack opening w . In the case of variable bond properties (heterogeneous reinforcement), the debonded length is a random variable.

The idealization of the composite can be described as a set of parallel 1D springs (representing the fibers) with tensile stiffness per unit length $E_f A_f$ coupled to a single 1D spring (representing the matrix) with the stiffness $E_m A_c (1 - V_f)$ through a (possibly random) frictional bond with the shear flow per unit length $2\pi r \tau$.

2.1.1 Probabilistic homogenization

It was explained in [4] that with the quasi-static crack opening w set as *indirect displacement control* variable, the composite stress can be kept tracking of also during the descending branch and a stable process is provided under all circumstances. A load controlled, σ_c , model would only be able to track the stress up to its peak value and a total displacement control, u , would be unstable in cases where the response exhibits snap-back behavior (see Fig. 1).

In composites with heterogeneous reinforcement individual fibers have variable properties and the composite stress is the normalized sum of their contributions to the bridging stress. It has been derived in [4] that as the number of fibers n_f grows large, the normalized sum of all fiber responses converges by the law of large numbers to the value of their average so that the composite response can be represented by the statistical average of individual fibers.

Let the fiber strain at the matrix crack position as a function of the crack opening w and the sampling space of the assumed random variables \mathbf{X} be denoted $\varepsilon_{f0, \mathbf{X}}(w, \mathbf{X})$. The resulting formula for the expected value of the composite stress σ_c (denoted as $\mu_{\sigma_c, \mathbf{X}}$) as a function of a non-negative crack opening w is given as

$$\mu_{\sigma_c, \mathbf{X}}(w) = E_f V_f E [\nu_f(r) \varepsilon_{f0, \mathbf{X}}(w, \mathbf{X})], \quad w \geq 0, \quad (1)$$

where the average is denoted by the expectation operator $E[\cdot]$ and the variable $\nu_f(r)$ was derived in [4] as

$$\nu_f(r) = \frac{r^2}{E[r^2]} \quad (2)$$

and can be viewed as a weight factor for fibers with respect to their cross-sectional area. The mean composite strength is defined as

$$\mu_{\sigma_c, \mathbf{X}}^* = \sup\{\mu_{\sigma_c, \mathbf{X}}(w); w \geq 0\}. \quad (3)$$

In order to evaluate the mean values given by Eqns. (1) and (3), the fiber crack bridge function $\varepsilon_{f, \mathbf{X}}(w, \mathbf{X})$ has to be resolved and the joint distribution function of the random variables must be provided [4, 23].

2.1.2 Fiber crack bridge function

To derive the ‘fiber crack bridge function’ in a straightforward way, we first assume that fibers have infinite strength and analyze the contribution of a single fiber within a composite crack bridge to the total transmitted stress. The aspect of finite fiber strength will be included later.

Even though the model flexibility allows for an arbitrary number of random variables, we consider only the bond strength τ to be a random variable for simplicity. Thus, the sampling space \mathbf{X} spans one dimension \mathbb{R} . The pullout of individual fibers from the matrix is simulated by the shear-lag model with infinite shear stiffness and a constant bond strength τ [24, 1, 2]. When the matrix crack opens by the amount w , the bridging fibers debond along the length a and transmit the force into the matrix. The transmitted force is a monotonic increasing function of the crack opening w , bond strength τ and the debonded length a , which depends on the random variables spanning the sampling space \mathbf{X} , i.e. $a = \mathcal{A}(w, \mathbf{X})$. For any debonded fiber, the differential equilibrium equation reads (see Fig. 1)

$$E_f \varepsilon'_{f, \mathbf{X}}(z) + T_z(z, \mathbf{X}) = 0, \quad (4)$$

with

$$\varepsilon'_{f, \mathbf{X}}(z) = \frac{d\varepsilon_{f, \mathbf{X}}(z)}{dz} = -\frac{T_z(z, \mathbf{X})}{E_f} \quad (5)$$

being the derivative of the fiber longitudinal strain with respect to z and $T_z(\mathbf{X}, z)$ the bond intensity given by

$$T_z(z, \mathbf{X}) = T(\mathbf{X}) \cdot \text{sign}(z). \quad (6)$$

Here, T is the shear flow per unit length normalized by the fiber cross-sectional area

$$T = \frac{2\pi r \tau}{\pi r^2} = \frac{2\tau}{r}. \quad (7)$$

In order to obtain the fiber strain at the crack plane, Eq. (5) is to be integrated and evaluated for $z = 0$. If fibers can freely debond to both sides without any restriction, the fiber strain is identical to the matrix strain at the end point of debonded lengths, i.e. $\varepsilon_{f, \mathbf{X}}(z = \pm a) = \varepsilon_m(z = \pm a)$ (see Fig. 1). At distances $|z| \geq a$, the fiber strain equals the matrix strain $\varepsilon_m(z)$ so that fibers and matrix form a compact composite cross-section with a unique longitudinal strain shared by both constituents. The expression for the fiber strain within the debonded range is obtained by integrating Eq. (5) and taking into consideration the above mentioned boundary conditions

$$\varepsilon_{f, \mathbf{X}}(w, z, \mathbf{X}) = \int_{-a}^z \varepsilon'_{f, \mathbf{X}}(x) dx = \varepsilon_m(-a) + \frac{T(\mathbf{X})a - T_z(z, \mathbf{X})z}{E_f}, \quad |z| < a \quad (8)$$

with $\varepsilon_m(-a) = \varepsilon_m(a)$ due to symmetry of the fiber strain about the crack plane $z = 0$. The dimension of $\varepsilon_{f, \mathbf{X}}$ is \mathbb{R}^{n+2} corresponding to the n dimensions of the sampling space \mathbf{X} , the dimension of the longitudinal position z and of the crack opening w . By the evaluation of the maximum fiber strain

$\varepsilon_{f0,\mathbf{X}}(w, \mathbf{X}) = \varepsilon_{f,\mathbf{X}}(w, z = 0, \mathbf{X})$, the dimensionality is reduced by one the resulting form is obtained as:

$$\varepsilon_{f0,\mathbf{X}}(w, \mathbf{X}) = \varepsilon_m(a) + \frac{T(\mathbf{X})a}{E_f}. \quad (9)$$

There are two unknowns in Eq. (9): the debonded length a and the longitudinal matrix strain $\varepsilon_m(a)$. To evaluate these unknowns, we define a differential equilibrium of stresses in the matrix with a kinematic constraint. The sought variables are then found as the solution of an initial value problem.

With the assumption of negligible shear deformations of the matrix (zero shear-lag thickness assumption), the differential equilibrium of matrix stresses in the longitudinal direction can be stated as

$$K_{cs}(z)\varepsilon'_m(z) - t(z) = 0, \quad (10)$$

where $\varepsilon'_m(z) = d\varepsilon_m(z)/dz$ is the derivative of the axial matrix strain with respect z , $t(z)$ is the longitudinal traction originating from the friction of debonded fibers at the fiber-matrix interface and $K_{cs}(z)$ is the axial stiffness of the compact composite cross-section. It is to be explained that the compact composite stiffness $K_{cs}(z)$ includes the stiffness of both matrix and bonded fibers, i.e. fibers with zero slip. Without explicitly describing all details of the derivation, we state the resulting form of the matrix strain derivative for a large number of fibers, exploiting asymptotic results of statistical averages

$$\varepsilon'_m(z) \approx \frac{\mu_{t,\mathbf{X}}(z)}{\mu_{K_{cs},\mathbf{X}}(z)}. \quad (11)$$

with

$$\mu_{K_{cs},\mathbf{X}}(z) = E_c - E_f V_f E[\nu_f(r) \cdot H(a - z)] \quad (12)$$

and

$$\mu_{t,\mathbf{X}}(z) = V_f E[T \nu_f(r) \cdot H(a - z)]. \quad (13)$$

being the averages of $t(z)$ and $K_{cs}(z)$, respectively, and $H(\cdot)$ denoting the Heaviside step function. With the initial value of zero matrix strain at the crack position, $\varepsilon_m(0) = 0$, we have an initial value problem, the solution of which is the unknown matrix strain needed for the evaluation of the fiber crack bridge function Eq. (9).

The additional equation needed for solving the unknown a is a kinematic constraint of the crack bridge problem stating that the crack opening is identical to all fibers irrespective of their random parameters from the sampling space \mathbf{X} . The crack opening is defined as the difference between the fiber and matrix strain integrated over the whole debonded range:

$$w = \int_{-a}^a \varepsilon_{f,\mathbf{X}}(\mathbf{X}, z) - \varepsilon_m(z) dz \quad (14)$$

which implicitly includes the debonded length a and relates it to the control variable – the crack opening w . Note that for a particular sampling point (vector of random parameters) X_i from the sampling domain \mathbf{X} , the crack opening given by Eq. (14) can be interpreted as the shaded area in Fig. 1. With the substitution of the implicit expression for a given by Eq. (14) into Eq. (11), a 2nd order ODE is obtained which can be integrated using a suitable numerical method to yield the matrix strain profile $\varepsilon_m(z)$ and, particularly, its value at $\varepsilon_m(a)$ needed for the fiber crack bridge function given by Eq. (9).

Recalling that the ultimate goal of the probabilistic crack bridge model (PCBM) is the simulation of a unidirectional composite with multiple cracks in series, the PCBM has to be able to take into account the interaction of neighboring cracks. When debonded lengths of fibers from two neighboring cracks connect, further debonding is not possible and the fibers act like clamped to the matrix at the point of the connection of their debonded lengths – the fiber slip is restrained. The position of the contact between the debonded zones can be with reasonable accuracy assumed to be at the half distance between two adjacent cracks. In general, the distances to adjacent cracks at both sides of a particular crack are different. The

Figure 2. Effect of boundary conditions on the fiber and matrix strain profiles: (a) free debonding; (b) one-sided restricted debonding; (c) clamped fibers - restricted debonding at both sides of the crack bridge.

half distance to the closer and more distant crack from the analyzed crack shall be denoted L_{\downarrow} and L_{\uparrow} , respectively (see Fig. 2). The effect of the symmetry condition is conveniently included in the model by adapting the integration ranges in Eq. (14) from a for free debonding to L_{\downarrow} for the closer adjacent crack or L_{\uparrow} for the crack further away. For reasons of brevity, we refer to the possibility of including finite fiber breaking strain to [4].

2.2 Probabilistic multiple cracking model

The kernel of the probabilistic multiple cracking model (PMCM) is the crack tracing algorithm. Its generic implementation can be combined with several types of crack bridge models with various assumptions about the material structure including the probabilistic crack bridge model (PCBM) introduced in the present paper.

Consider an intermediate state of a loaded specimen covering the domain $x \in \langle 0, L_c \rangle$ with a set of K existing cracks at the positions $\mathbf{X}^{(K)} = \{X_k\}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$. Let the composite stress σ_c , which is constant along the cracked specimen, represent the control loading variable. Its value at the initiation of the K^{th} crack is denoted $\sigma_c^{(K)}$. The goal of the crack tracing algorithm is to find the next crack, i.e. the load level $\sigma_c^{(K+1)} > \sigma_c^{(K)}$ and the position X_{K+1} .

Let us assume that the matrix tensile strength is a function of the global spatial coordinate x (e.g. a constant or representation of a random field) given as $\sigma_{\text{mu}} = \Sigma_{\text{mu}}(x)$ and the matrix stress state respecting the K existing cracks is provided in the form

$$\sigma_{\text{m}}^{(K)} = \Sigma_{\text{m}} \left(\sigma_c, x, \mathbf{X}^{(K)}, \Theta_{\text{CB}} \right), \quad (15)$$

with Θ_{CB} being a vector of parameters required by the particular model. Then, the load σ_c initiating a new crack at any point x of the tensile specimen can be obtained by solving the equation

$$\Sigma(x) := \left\{ \sigma_c \mid \Sigma_{\text{m}} \left(\sigma_c, x, \mathbf{X}^{(K)}, \Theta_{\text{CB}} \right) = \Sigma_{\text{mu}}(x) \right\}. \quad (16)$$

The sought composite stress $\sigma_c^{(K+1)}$ initiating the next crack and the position of this crack X_{K+1} are evaluated by identifying the minimum of $\Sigma(x)$ along $x \in (0, L_c)$:

$$\sigma_c^{(K+1)} = \min_{x \in (0, L_c)} \Sigma(x), \quad X_{K+1} = \arg \min_{x \in (0, L_c)} \Sigma(x). \quad (17)$$

The history of cracks with associated state variables is obtained by incremental evaluation of Eq. (16) and Eq. (17) for an incremented crack counter $K = K + 1$. In the initial state $K = 0$ without a crack, the matrix stress is constant along the specimen and can be obtained explicitly using the rule of mixtures. The algorithm ends if no solution to Eq. (16) is found for any σ_c and x indicating a saturated cracking state with K_{sat} cracks. The ultimate failure is defined by the mean fiber strength attained in the weakest crack bridge.

Figure 3. Calibration of τ and σ_{mu} distribution hyper-parameters: (a) single crack bridge experiments fitted by the probabilistic crack bridge model (τ calibration); (b) tensile tests with multiple matrix cracking fitted by the probabilistic multiple cracking model (σ_{mu} calibration).

With the identified history of the matrix cracking states $K = 1, 2, \dots, K_{sat}$ at hand, the composite strains ϵ_c corresponding to the load σ_c given the current crack positions $\mathbf{X}^{(K)}$ can be evaluated as

$$\epsilon_c^{(K)} = \frac{1}{L_c} \left[\sum_{k=1}^K w_k^{(K)} + \frac{1}{E_m} \int_0^{L_c} \sigma_m^{(K)} dz \right]. \quad (18)$$

The K crack openings $w_k^{(K)}$, $k = 1, 2, \dots, K$ and the assembled matrix stress $\sigma_m^{(K)}$ prescribed by Eq. (15) have to be provided crack bridge model.

3. CALIBRATION AND VALIDATION

In order to assess the validity of the model, its predictive capabilities were tested against experimental data obtained from tensile tests with textile reinforced concrete (TRC). TRC with dry (non-impregnated) carbon yarns exhibits a high degree of reinforcement heterogeneity due to the imperfect penetration of the cement-based matrix into the multi-filament yarn structure [4, 25].

3.1 Experimental setup

TRC specimens with three levels of fiber volume fraction, $V_f = 0.1\%$, 1.0% and 1.5% , have been produced and subjected to tensile loading after 28 days of curing. Specimens with $V_f = 0.1\%$ are on purpose reinforced below the critical value that would ensure multiple matrix cracks. The reasoning behind the low V_f value is the separation of the fiber debonding and rupturing effects from the matrix cracking in these experiments which enables us to use the probabilistic crack bridge model (PCBM) for bond strength calibration. For the calibration of the model, we use a representative experimental curve obtained by averaging the measured forces, see dashed curve in Fig. 3a. This average force is evaluated as

$$\bar{F}(w) = \frac{1}{N_{CB}} \sum_{i=1}^{N_{CB}} F_i(w). \quad (19)$$

The specimens with $V_f = 1.0\%$ and 1.5% formed multiple matrix cracks which were detected with the optical deformation measuring system ARAMIS. These experiments are to be simulated by the probabilistic multiple cracking model (PMCM).

3.2 Calibration of random parameters

There are 7 parameters that need to be provided as input for the probabilistic multiple model if all of them are considered as deterministic. However, some of the parameters are inherently random in nature which introduces additional unknowns into the model formulation – descriptors of their statistical distributions. We refer to the parameters of the distributions as hyper-parameters and denote them by the vector $\Theta_{\mathbf{X}}$ with \mathbf{X} referring to the random model parameter.

Carbon fibers have a random tensile breaking strain ξ determined by the weakest flaw in the material structure, the bond strength τ is random due to the irregular matrix penetration into the yarn structure and the matrix tensile strength is random due to its heterogeneous material structure and (quasi) brittle failure mode. The remaining parameters are assumed to be deterministic: From the product specifications, the fiber radius is given as $r = 3.5 \mu\text{m}$. Based on tensile tests with Toho Tenax carbon yarns (length 300 mm, fineness 1600 tex) performed at the RWTH University (Institute of Textile Technology), the measured modulus of elasticity is $E_f = 182 \text{ GPa}$. Adapted from compression tests performed at the same university (Institute of Structural Materials), the modulus of elasticity of the matrix is set to $E_m = 25 \text{ GPa}$.

Fiber breaking strain We use the common assumption of compound Poisson process for the spatial and severity distribution of fiber flaws with the **hyper-parameters** shape m_f and scale s_f related to the reference volume $V_0 = 1 \text{ mm}^3$. It can be derived that the breaking strain of a fiber embedded in matrix with constant frictional stress at their interface follows the two-parameter Weibull distribution

$$\xi \sim G_{\xi}(\varepsilon_{f0}) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\langle \frac{\varepsilon_{f0}}{\varepsilon_0} \right\rangle^{m_f+1} \right]. \quad (20)$$

For a single isolated crack bridge, where a triangular fiber strain profile can be assumed, the parameter

$$\varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{T(m_f + 1)s_f^{m_f}V_0}{2E_f\pi r^2} \right)^{1/(m_f+1)}, \quad \text{for } a < \ell_{CS}/2 \quad (21)$$

and for multiple cracking, the ‘saw-tooth’ profile of the fiber strain is conveniently approximated by a constant so that

$$\varepsilon_0 = \left(\frac{T s_f^{m_f} V_0}{2E_f \pi r^2} \right)^{1/(m_f+1)}, \quad \text{for } a > \ell_{CS}/2 \quad (22)$$

with a being the debonded length and ℓ_{CS} the crack spacing. Detailed derivations of the above can be found e.g. in [4, 9, 19].

The parameters of the distribution are identified from dry filament tests at variable gauge lengths performed at the Leibniz Institute of Polymer Research (Dresden, Germany) [26]. It can be found e.g. in [26] that the mean breaking strain of a fiber of length L is given by

$$\mu_{\varepsilon_f}^*(L, s_f, m_f) = (\pi r^2 L)^{-1/m_f} s_f \Gamma(1 + 1/m_f), \quad (23)$$

where s_f is the characteristic breaking strain of a reference unit volume $V_0 = 1 \text{ mm}^3$ and m_f the shape parameter of the breaking strain distribution.

Filaments at gauge lengths 50 mm and 100 mm were tested with mean fiber breaking strains 1.81% and 1.63%, respectively. The parameters of G_{ξ} were obtained as the solution of two equations Eq. (23) with the two lengths and averages of measured breaking strains: $m_f = 6.7$ and $s_f = 7.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$. We will refer to these hyper-parameters as $\hat{\Theta}_{\xi}$.

Bond strength One possible mathematical function that describes the distribution of the effective bond strength in a multifilament yarn in cement-based matrix is the three-parameter gamma distribution

$$\tau \sim G_{\tau}(\tau; m_{\tau}, s_{\tau}) = \frac{\gamma(m_{\tau}, (\tau - l_{\tau})/s_{\tau})}{\Gamma(m_{\tau})} \quad (24)$$

Figure 4. Validation of the model: (a) predicted crack spacing evolution (black curves) compared to measured saturated crack spacing (gray curves); (b) predicted force-strain responses for a composite with fiber volume fraction $V_f = 1.5\%$.

with $\gamma(x, y)$ being the lower incomplete gamma function and $\Gamma(x)$ the complete gamma function. The **hyper-parameters** subject to calibration are: shape m_τ , scale s_τ and location l_τ .

These three hyper-parameters can be calibrated independently of the matrix strength parameters by fitting the single crack bridge experiment responses with the PCBM. For convenience, we will refer to the three hyper-parameters by the vector $\Theta_\tau = \{s_\tau, m_\tau, l_\tau\}$. The objective function $R_{CB}(\Theta_\tau)$ whose minimum identifies the sought hyper-parameters $\hat{\Theta}_\tau$ can be written as the integrated squared error between the average crack bridge force $\bar{F}(w)$ measured in the single crack bridge experiments (Eq. 19) and the mean crack bridge force $\mu_F(w, \Theta_\tau)$ evaluated by the PCBM. The mean crack bridge force $\mu_F(w, \Theta_\tau) = \mu_{\sigma_c}(w, \Theta_\tau)A_c$ with $\mu_{\sigma_c}(w, \Theta_\tau)$ given by Eq. (1) and A_c being the composite cross-sectional area. The error is integrated over w up to an upper threshold value w_{\max}

$$R_{CB}(\Theta_\tau) = \int_0^{w_{\max}} \left[\bar{F}(w) - \mu_F(w; \Theta_\tau, \hat{\Theta}_\xi) \right]^2 dw. \quad (25)$$

Fig. 3d shows the PCBM response $\mu_{\sigma_c}(w, \hat{\Theta}_\tau, \hat{\Theta}_\xi)A_c$ and the fitted averaged experimental curve.

Matrix strength The tensile strength of the cement-based matrix is represented by the two-parameter Weibull distribution

$$\sigma_{\text{mu}} \sim \mathcal{W}_{\sigma_{\text{mu}}}(\sigma_m) = 1 - \exp \left[- \left\langle \frac{\sigma_m}{s_m} \right\rangle^{m_m} \right], \quad (26)$$

where the shape m_m and scale s_m are the model's **hyper-parameters**. The strength is assumed to be deterministic within a single specimen but variable among specimens.

In order to identify the two hyper-parameters defining the matrix tensile strength distribution, $\hat{\Theta}_m \in \Theta_m = \{s_m, m_m\}$, we utilize the first cracking stresses of the five specimens and infer on the parameters of their distribution by the maximum likelihood method. The parameters obtained this way are: $m_m = 11.2$ and $s_m = 3.15$. Responses of the model with the calibrated vectors $\hat{\Theta}_\xi$, $\hat{\Theta}_\tau$ and five samples from the σ_{mu} distribution with the calibrated parameters $\hat{\Theta}_m$ are depicted in and Fig. 3b.

3.3 Prediction and validation

We now proceed to the prediction of the response of a composite with $V_f = 1.5\%$. It has been observed experimentally and studied theoretically that the first cracking stress is elevated with increased

fiber volume fraction [27]. In the cited references, researchers provide a relationship for the matrix strength increase with increased V_f , which yields the factors 1.34 between $V_f = 1.0\%$ and $V_f = 1.5\%$.

The force-strain curves and crack spacing evolution evaluated by the PMCM with the calibrated $\hat{\Theta}_\xi$, $\hat{\Theta}_\tau$ and five matrix strength samples from the $\sigma_{mu}(m_m, s_m)$ distribution (samples: 4.71, 3.98, 4.36, 3.99 and 4.15 MPa) are depicted in Fig. 4.

Observing the force-strain response in Fig. 4b, the fit between model prediction and experiments seems to be acceptable, the first cracking stresses and the multiple cracking stage are captured with good accuracy, but in the third (linear) range, there is difference in stiffness. While the model predicts the $E_f V_f$ composite stiffness, the experimentally measured stiffness increases during the loading process by a higher amount than what would simply correspond to the increased fiber volume fraction.

Fig. 4a depicts the prediction of the crack spacing evolution and its validation with the experimentally obtained crack spacing evolution. The averages of the measured and predicted saturated crack spacing are 13.6 mm and 16.5 mm rendering a difference of 1.9 mm or $\approx 20\%$.

4. CONCLUSIONS

It has been demonstrated that the multiscale probabilistic multiple cracking model is able to predict the behavior of fibrous composites with heterogeneous reinforcement subjected to tensile loading given the material parameters and their distribution. For the calibration of the material parameters, we have used tensile tests on single filaments textile reinforced concrete specimens with two levels of fiber volume fraction. With the obtained parameters, we have predicted crack spacing, ultimate strength and force-strain response of textile reinforced concrete with extrapolated fiber volume fraction.

Intermediate state: The probabilistic multiple cracking model is capable of reproducing and predicting the force-strain response of the composite, the process of multiple cracking and the saturated state which includes crack spacing (and the closely related crack widths), see Figs. 3 and 4. These predictive capabilities imply that the model reflects the random bond structure and the resulting stress transfer between the fibrous reinforcement and matrix in a fairly accurate manner.

Ultimate state: In the accompanying experiments, the average measured fiber strength of the crack bridge experiments and the multiple cracking experiments with $V_f = 1.0\%$ and $V_f = 1.5\%$ were 614 MPa, 1201 MPa and 1373 MPa, respectively. This corresponds to a respective 96% and 124% increase in fiber strength compared to the fiber strength measured in the crack bridge experiments. Strength variations of this magnitude are considerable and have to be taken into account when designing composites with heterogeneous reinforcement. We have provided an explanation of this phenomenon based on differences in crack spacing in [4].

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